

Factoring of the Smarandache Factorial Product Sequence,
by Micha Fleuren

SmFactProd(1): 2
PRIME!

SmFactProd(2): 3
PRIME!

SmFactProd(3): 13
PRIME!

SmFactProd(4): 289
17^2

SmFactProd(5): 34561
17.19.107

SmFactProd(6): 24883201
7.1789.1987

SmFactProd(7): 125411328001
PRIME!

SmFactProd(8): 5056584744960001
11.1249.1709.215357551

SmFactProd(9): 1834933472251084800001
11.19.421.44119.472678970411

SmFactProd(10): 6658606584104736522240000001
3646874959291.1825839015165811

SmFactProd(11): 265790267296391946810949632000000001
29.61.173.40570131534227.21407143589211599

SmFactProd(12): 127313963299399416749559771247411200000000001
23.74735863.74066043884039177532164334455677649

SmFactProd(13): 79278669759579679560737708640087148855296000000000001
41.59093.19805293.5167320614726209.3197347049764339148151721

SmFactProd(14):
6911378958249271294348680050646273456284741350195200000000000001
PRIME!

SmFactProd(15):
9037833111237114226297952156863073633502324773159974836633600000000000000
0001

61.79.16267.4372493.3156524936639.107881060677639294707.77431267662810055
5775512924233

SmFactProd(16):
1890966832292234727042877370627225068196418587883634153182519380410368000
000000000000000001

19.181.76836932794965823735044563.715618757058191051520893634315651301528
6056246520929602574293

SmFactProd(17):
6725931291928651303342176314739166588641223328825779796752772116838392389
728993280000000000000000000001

19.37.827.358867.32237255981343748914565008735692606293838501970984158468
01085781525194808474596045243946487263

